

Effectiveness of Government Social Assistance Programs (Case Study of the Family Hope Program (PKH) in Bandar Lampung)

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ABSTRACT: The Family Hope Program (PKH) is a conditional social assistance program aimed at reducing poverty and improving the welfare of the poor. However, its implementation still faces issues of inaccurate targeting, including inclusion and exclusion errors. This study aims to (1) determine the effectiveness of PKH implementation in 2022 in Bandar Lampung City and (2) identify the occurrence of inclusion errors. This study used a quantitative approach with primary and secondary data analyzed using descriptive statistics. PKH effectiveness was analyzed based on the accuracy of beneficiary targeting. The results indicate that PKH implementation in Bandar Lampung City in 2022 was not fully effective, as indicated by the discovery of 13% of PKH recipients who did not meet the beneficiary criteria (inclusion error). These households have characteristics of relatively higher incomes, greater electricity capacity, and better education and employment of the head of the family compared to the general poor.

KEYWORDS: Family Hope Program, program effectiveness, inclusion error, logistic regression, poverty indicators.

I. INTRODUCTION

Poverty continues to be a global issue for communities and countries. Various efforts have been made to reduce poverty. Combating poverty is not solely the responsibility of the government but also the community itself (Asih et al., 2022; Desi, 2020). The government is actively working to address poverty by implementing various policies. Poverty does not simply occur; it can be seen from several aspects, such as the inability to meet income, which results in a lack of basic needs for families (Salasiah et al., 2024; Syahril & Desrina, 2021). Inequality in residential areas, unproductive habits, and low human resources are all factors contributing to poverty.

Poverty and well-being are closely linked, with improved well-being being a key indicator of success in poverty alleviation. Well-being encompasses the fulfillment of basic needs such as education, health care, and adequate economic access. Poverty, if not addressed effectively, can lead to wider social inequality, exacerbate the intergenerational cycle of poverty, and hinder a country's economic development. Therefore, various government-run social programs, such as the Family Hope Program (PKH), play a crucial role in providing social protection and improving the quality of life for the poor, enabling them to escape the poverty trap and achieve greater well-being.

The government, which operates under the Ministry of Social Affairs, the Ministry of Finance, the Ministry of Health, and others, also works together to address public welfare issues. The Ministry of Finance allocates funds, including those covering health, social protection, MSME support, and the state budget. With such a large amount, it is hoped that both the public and the government can use the budget appropriately. The Ministry of Social Affairs issues social assistance programs for the people as an effort to alleviate poverty, including the Food Program, Rastha Social Assistance/Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT), and the Family Hope Program (PKH). One reason why researchers were interested in choosing the Family Hope Program (PKH) for their research is because the Family Hope Program (PKH) is a flagship program of the Ministry of Social Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia that directly reaches the community with the aim of social protection and poverty alleviation.

Family Hope Program (PKH) namely a program providing conditional social assistance to poor families who are designated as Beneficiary Families (KPM) provided quarterly via electronic money in collaboration with the Association of State Banks (HIMBARA) as a distributor (Aeda & Jannah, 2022; Arif et al., 2024; Ashar & Pratama, 2024). As part of poverty alleviation efforts through the provision of non-cash social assistance, PKH is expected to be able to help poor families in the short term. The PKH

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program aims to improve the quality of human resources, especially in education and health, in the Very Poor Household/Extremely Poor Family group (Syahrial & Desrina, 2021). As one of the poverty alleviation efforts, the Family Hope Program (PKH) is an important instrument in improving the welfare of poor communities in various regions, including in Lampung Province. With a broad and diverse coverage area, the implementation of PKH in Lampung aims to ensure that this social assistance can reach beneficiary families evenly, especially in areas with high poverty rates. Through collaboration with various parties, including local governments and financial institutions, PKH is expected to have a positive impact on improving the quality of life of the people of Lampung, especially in the aspects of education and health.

The following is data on PKH assistance recipients in regencies/cities throughout Lampung province in 2022:

Figure 1. Number of KPM Recipients PKH assistance for districts /cities in Lampung Province in 2022

Based on Figure 1, it can be seen that the amount of social assistance provided by the Ministry of Social Affairs in Lampung Province is still high in 2022. All regencies and cities in Lampung Province, including Bandar Lampung City, received Family Hope Program Assistance. Bandar Lampung City in 2022 received Family Hope Program Assistance for 33,017 KPM, placing Bandar Lampung City as the sixth largest recipient of Family Hope Program Assistance in Lampung Province. Bandar Lampung City is the capital of Lampung Province and is the center of government, social, political, educational and cultural activities as well as economic activities, this is what makes Bandar Lampung City a barometer and benchmark in various fields including in the field of poverty alleviation, one of which is in the field of the Family Hope Program (PKH).

The Family Hope Program (PKH) faces various challenges in the field related to the implementation of the 5T principles (accurate targeting, accurate amount, timely delivery, and accurate administration). Invalid recipient data results in mistargeting of aid, with recipients who do not meet the criteria still receiving aid, while deserving poor families are overlooked (Asahan Regency Social Service, 2024). Discrepancies in aid amounts also frequently occur due to administrative issues, such as non-distributed Prosperous Family Cards (KKS) or duplicate accounts (Sendouw et al., 2023). Aid distribution is often delayed, especially during the pandemic, impacting the livelihoods of those in need (Muga et al., 2021). Furthermore, aid use does not always align with program objectives due to a lack of verification and monitoring by PKH facilitators (Rohman et al., 2024). Administrative issues such as errors in bank area distribution or suboptimal validation of beneficiary data also hamper program efficiency (Megaartha, 2022).

In practice, the Family Hope Program (PKH) is not without its challenges. In 2019, there were reports of illegal levies (pungli) perpetrated by certain facilitators on Beneficiary Families (KPM). Furthermore, Bandar Lampung City serves as a barometer and benchmark in various fields, including poverty alleviation, one of which is the Family Hope Program (PKH). This is one of the reasons researchers were interested in choosing Bandar Lampung as their research location. This government program aims to reduce poverty and improve the standard of living of the community, especially for the underprivileged, so that they can realize prosperous families (Aeda & Jannah, 2022; Ali & Hafasnuddin, 2021; Annisya & Alikha Novira, 2023).

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Previous research on the Family Hope Program (PKH) has focused largely on implementation effectiveness, targeting accuracy, and its impact on the welfare of the poor. However, there is still a research gap in comprehensively measuring PKH effectiveness based on the 5T indicators (Right Target, Right Amount, Right Time, Right Purpose, and Right Administration), particularly in Bandar Lampung City as one of the regions with a significant number of PKH recipients. Furthermore, previous research has not thoroughly examined the dominant factors that most influence the success of this program in improving community welfare. Therefore, this study offers novelty by analyzing PKH effectiveness more specifically in Bandar Lampung City and identifying the dominant factors that influence program success, so that the results can provide recommendations for improving more effective social policies.

Therefore, it is hoped that the implementation of the Family Hope social assistance program can run effectively and efficiently so that the stated objectives can be achieved. Therefore, evaluation of program implementation is necessary by measuring the program's effectiveness. The effectiveness of a program can be seen from the final results, namely the extent to which the program's objectives have been achieved. To determine the effectiveness of a program's implementation, an analysis can be conducted by measuring its effectiveness using various indicators based on existing concepts and theories. This effectiveness can be viewed from various perspectives, depending on who is assessing and interpreting it. Therefore, assessing the level of program suitability is one way to measure program effectiveness.

Based on the description above, this research was conducted to determine the effectiveness of PKH, the effectiveness of PKH that will be studied in this research is whether PKH assistance is on target, in the right amount, on time, on purpose, and in the right administration.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. PKH Social Assistance

The Family Hope Program, hereinafter referred to as PKH, is a conditional social assistance program for poor families (KM) designated as PKH beneficiary families (Fadhli & Nazila, 2023). As an effort to accelerate poverty alleviation, the Indonesian government has implemented PKH since 2007. This social protection program, also known internationally as Conditional Cash Transfers (CCT), has proven quite successful in alleviating poverty in these countries, especially the problem of chronic poverty.

Legal Basis of the Family Hope Program (PKH):

- a. Law Number 40 of 2004 concerning the National Social Security System
- b. Law Number 13 of 2011 concerning the Handling of the Poor
- c. Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 63 of 2019
- d. Presidential Instruction Number 3 of 2010 concerning the Equitable Development Program, Attachment Point 1 concerning Improvements to the Implementation of the Family Hope Program
- e. Presidential Instruction Number 1 of 2013 concerning the Prevention and Eradication of Corruption, attachment point 46 concerning the Implementation of Transparency in the Distribution of Conditional Direct Cash Assistance for Very Poor Families (KSM) as Participants in the Family Hope Program (PKH).
- f. Regulation of the Minister of Social Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1 of 2018.

The overall goal of the Family Hope Program (PKH) is to reduce poverty and break the cycle of poverty, improve human resources, and change the behavior of beneficiaries who are relatively less conducive to improving welfare. This goal also serves as an effort to accelerate the achievement of *the Millennium Development Goals* (MDGs).

The specific objectives of PKH are:

- a. Improving the education level of KPM children
- b. Improving the health status of pregnant and postpartum mothers and the nutrition of toddlers
- c. Improving access to education and health services, especially for children of Beneficiary Families (KPM).

PKH recipients

PKH Social Assistance is provided to registered very poor families. in the Integrated Social Welfare Data (DTKS) and has a Prosperous Family Card, hereinafter referred to as Beneficiary Family (KPM) who fulfills one or more criteria:

- a. Pregnant mother
- b. Toddler
- c. Elementary school/Islamic elementary school/equivalent students
- d. Junior high school/Islamic junior high school/equivalent students
- e. High school/Islamic high school/equivalent students

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Furthermore, assistance is provided in non-cash form through the State-Owned Bank Association (Himbara). In the distribution of PKH social assistance, there are four stages in one year.

Family Hope Program (PKH) Assistance Indicators

The success of the Family Hope Program (PKH) refers to the 2007 PKH General Guidelines, which are measured based on the level of achievement of the 5T indicators: right on target, right amount, right time, right purpose and right administration.

a. Right on target

Planning is carried out to determine the location and number of prospective KPM. The location and number of prospective KPM are sourced from the Integrated Social Welfare Data (DTKS) or can be excluded for victims of natural disasters, social disasters and remote indigenous communities (KAT). The determination of prospective PKH KPM is determined by the Director of Family Social Security of the Ministry of Social Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia (Ministry of Social Affairs, 2021). After the prospective PKH KPM is determined by the Director of Family Social Security of the Ministry of Social Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia, the data is sent to the PKH facilitator for initial socialization and validation by the PKH facilitator in coordination with the Social Service, Sub-district Head and Village Head.

To determine whether someone is poor, PKH Companions refer to the government's poverty criteria, established by the Central Statistics Agency (BPS). The 14 poverty criteria can be used as a benchmark for assessing whether someone is poor. Of these 14 poverty criteria, a person is considered poor and eligible for social assistance if at least nine of them are met.

1. The floor area of residential buildings is less than 8m² per person.
2. The type of residential floor is made of dirt/bamboo/cheap wood.
3. Types of residential walls made of bamboo/rumbia/low quality wood/unplastered walls.
4. Do not have defecation facilities/shared with other households.
5. Household lighting sources do not use electricity.
6. The source of drinking water comes from wells/unprotected springs/rivers/rainwater.
7. The fuel for daily cooking is firewood/charcoal/kerosene.
8. Only consume meat/milk/chicken once a week.
9. Only buy one new set of clothes a year.
10. Only able to eat once/twice a day.
11. Unable to pay for medical expenses at the Community Health Center/Polyclinic.
12. The source of income for the head of the household is: farmer with a land area of 500m² · farm laborer, fisherman, construction worker, plantation worker or other work with income below Rp. 600,000 per month.
13. Head of household's highest education: no school/did not finish elementary school/finished elementary school.
14. Do not have savings or easily sold goods with a minimum value of Rp. 500,000, such as a motorcycle on credit or non-credit, gold, livestock, motorboat, or other capital goods.

b. Exact amount

PKH assistance amount according to category 2023:

Figure 2 PKH Social Assistance in 2022

Source: Lampung Province PPKH Operator, 2022

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Based on the provisions above, the effectiveness of the accuracy of the amount of the PKH Assistance Program can be measured, indicated by the amount of money received by KPM in accordance with the Components and there are no deductions from irresponsible individuals.

c. On time

The distribution of PKH social assistance is determined by the Ministry of Social Affairs and in coordination with the Distributing Bank, namely there are four stages in one year:

Figure 3 Stages in PKH distribution in 2022

Source: Lampung Province PPKH Operator, 2022

Based on the provisions above, the effectiveness of the timeliness of the PKH Assistance Program can be measured, as shown by its implementation according to the established schedule.

d. Right on Target

In the Minister of Social Affairs Regulation 1/2018, it is stated that PKH aims to create behavioral changes and independence of KPM in accessing health, education and social welfare services that will improve the standard of living of KPM and reduce the burden and increase the income of poor and vulnerable families, thereby reducing poverty and inequality. PKH distribution is carried out through ATMs, so that transactions using the ATM recipients can ensure the appropriateness of the amount of assistance that should be received with the balance in the ATM. To ensure that the PKH assistance received is appropriately targeted, monitoring and assistance are carried out by PKH Companions through the Family Capacity Building Meeting (P2K2) activities which are held routinely every month. In addition, visits (*home visits*) are also carried out routinely by PKH Companions. PKH Companions also make regular visits to the schools of students who are part of the PKH KPM to determine the activeness (presence) of students in participating in learning at school and health facilities.

Regarding the use of the aid money received by KPM, the City PKH Coordinator stated that PKH facilitators provide guidance to ensure the funds are used as directed, including for the health needs of pregnant women and young children, the education needs of school-age children, and the needs of the elderly and people with disabilities. However, so far there has been no mechanism for controlling the use of aid funds to ensure that they are used according to regulations and are not misused, for example, to purchase cigarettes or other consumer goods.

e. Proper Administration

Once the aid has been confirmed to have been deposited into each recipient's account, the PKH facilitator informs the recipient, who can then withdraw the aid through an ATM. PKH reporting is carried out both through the PKH information system and in writing. All PKH implementers, whether Coordinators or Facilitators, are required to report all routine activities through the designated information system application.

Based on the provisions above, the effectiveness of the accuracy of the administration of the PKH Assistance Program can be measured, as indicated by the PKH Companions being obliged to report every activity carried out routinely in writing and through the information system application (SIK-NG and eSDM PKH).

DATA AND METHOD

This study employed a *mixed methods approach* , namely descriptive qualitative and quantitative approaches, to explore the effectiveness of the Family Hope Program (PKH) in depth. The qualitative approach was conducted through data collection techniques such as in-depth interviews, direct observation, and document analysis (Fadli, 2021). The in-depth interviews aimed to explore the subjective experiences of beneficiaries, program facilitators, and policymakers regarding the program's impact on

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community well-being. Observations provided a direct view of program implementation, while documentation provided relevant secondary data to support the analysis. This approach provided a holistic understanding of how PKH impacts the lives of beneficiaries, particularly in social, economic, educational, and health aspects.

Determination of the number of research samples from PKH Beneficiary elements was carried out using the Slovin formula approach, namely (Hermawan & Amirullah, 2021):

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where:

n = Sample size

N = Population

e = Percentage of unboundedness due to desired sampling error, as much as 10%.

$$n = \frac{33.017}{1 + 33.017(10\%)^2}$$

$$n = 99,698 = 100 \text{ people.}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Lampung is a province at the southern tip of Sumatra Island. Its capital and center of government is in Bandar Lampung City. This province has two cities, namely Bandar Lampung and Metro, and 13 regencies, namely West Lampung Regency, Tanggamus Regency, South Lampung Regency, East Lampung Regency, Central Lampung Regency, North Lampung Regency, Way Kanan Regency, Tulang Bawang Regency, Pesawaran Regency, Pringsewu Regency, Mesuji Regency, West Tulang Bawang Regency, and West Pesisir Regency. According to the Central Statistics Agency of Bandar Lampung City, the percentage of poor people is 8.21% of the total population or 90,510 residents are poor. Poverty in Bandar Lampung City is relatively lower compared to the average percentage of poor people in Indonesia (9.54%).

EFFECTIVENESS OF PKH IN BANDAR LAMPUNG CITY

This section will discuss the effectiveness of the Family Hope Program (PKH) implementation in Bandar Lampung City as one of the government's social protection policy instruments in poverty alleviation efforts. According to the government's perception, the effectiveness analysis was conducted using the 5T approach, namely right on target, right amount, right on time, right purpose, and right administration, which is used to assess the suitability between policy design and program implementation in the field. This discussion links the empirical findings of the study with the concept of public policy effectiveness and the socio-economic conditions of the recipient community, so it is expected to provide an overview of the achievements and obstacles of PKH in improving the welfare of beneficiary families in Bandar Lampung City. Table 1 shows the effectiveness of PKH in Bandar Lampung City.

Table 1 Effectiveness of the PKH program in Bandar Lampung City

Indicator	Agree	Don't agree
Right on target	87%	13%
Exact Amount	99%	1%
On time	97%	3%
Right on Target	98%	2%
Proper Administration	98%	2%

The 5T indicators, which include on-target, on-quantity, on-time, on-purpose, and on-administration, in the PKH program in Bandar Lampung City have generally demonstrated the program's effectiveness. 87% of respondents stated that the PKH program was on-target, 99% stated that the amount was on-quantity, 97% stated that it was on-time, 98% stated that it was on-purpose, and 98% stated that it was on-administration. The following details the results of the study on respondents in Bandar Lampung City.

Right on target

The effectiveness of the Family Hope Program (PKH) is determined by the accuracy of the determination of Beneficiary Families (KPM) based on the Integrated Social Welfare Data (DTKS). Research observations indicate that the majority of PKH recipients in

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Bandar Lampung meet the eligibility criteria. However, some recipients from relatively better economic circumstances are still registered as beneficiaries. This data is shown in Table 2.

Table 21 KPM who meets 9 criteria recipient benefit

Number of KPM samples	Meet 9 criteria	Does not meet 9 criteria
100	87	13

Table 2 shows the distribution of beneficiary families (KPM) of the Family Hope Program (PKH) in Bandar Lampung City based on their compliance with the criteria for assistance. Of the 100 KPM sampled in the study, 87 KPM (87%) met the criteria for PKH, while 13 KPM (13%) did not meet the established criteria.

These results indicate that the overall implementation of the Family Hope Program (PKH) in Bandar Lampung City has been quite effective in terms of targeting, as the majority of assistance has been received by households that meet the participation criteria. However, the finding of 13% of beneficiary families (KPM) who did not meet the criteria indicates inaccurate targeting in determining beneficiaries. This condition reflects an *inclusion error*, where households that are relatively economically disadvantaged are still listed as beneficiaries. This phenomenon can be explained through the findings of a logistic regression analysis, which shows that the determination of PKH recipient status is influenced by a combination of several socioeconomic variables, not solely by a single indicator.

Thus, the 13% of PKH recipients who do not fully meet the criteria can be understood as a consequence of the dynamic and multidimensional targeting mechanism and limitations in updating DTKS data. This condition reflects an inclusion error, not solely due to errors in determining beneficiaries, but also due to changes in household socioeconomic conditions that have not been fully accommodated in the data collection system.

The selection of PKH beneficiary areas and families (KPM) is part of the initial mechanism and procedures before the PKH program is implemented in the operational phase. According to PKH facilitators, the determination of locations and KPM is entirely determined by the central government, specifically the Ministry of Social Affairs. The determination of KPM is based on several criteria, including the economic condition of vulnerable families, data collection and verification results, the level of social vulnerability and poverty, the number of dependents in the family, household conditions, and family participation in education and health programs. These criteria are supported by complete administrative data such as Family Cards, copies of ID cards, the Healthy Indonesia Card (KIS), the Smart Indonesia Card (KIP), and other supporting documents.

PKH recipients who no longer meet the beneficiary criteria should apply for Independent Graduation, which is to request termination of PKH assistance participation, thus providing opportunities for other prospective recipients. According to PKH facilitators, there are two causes for PKH recipient graduation (PKH recipients whose assistance is terminated by the Ministry of Social Affairs). The first is Independent Graduation (voluntary), independent graduation occurs when the beneficiary family feels capable and voluntarily declares to leave PKH. The second is Natural Graduation (Ineligible), Natural graduation occurs when KPM no longer meets the required components in PKH. These components are pregnant women, toddlers, school children, the elderly, and people with disabilities.

Figure 4 Interview with PKH Companion

Interview with PKH facilitator regarding the PKH KPM targeting process:

"Before determining aid recipients, initial socialization and validation is carried out for prospective KPM"

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"Data updates are carried out routinely and through home visits"

Interviews revealed that prior to determining aid recipients, initial outreach and validation were conducted with prospective Beneficiary Families (KPM). PKH Facilitators explained that the targeting process relies not only on administrative data but also involves verifying the actual conditions of households through a data update mechanism.

The PKH facilitator also explained that data updates are conducted through the DTKS (Integrated Social Welfare Data), which is regularly updated, and supplemented by home visits to ensure the family's socioeconomic condition aligns with PKH criteria. These home visits enable facilitators to identify changes in the household's economic condition, such as improvements in welfare or changes in family structure, thereby minimizing the potential for targeting errors.

Validation and *home visit activity* through strengthening and mentoring PKH human resources, conducted 12 times a year, and conducting periodic evaluations annually. These measures can minimize inaccurate targeting of PKH recipients.

Exact Amount

The aspect of the appropriate amount in the implementation of the Family Hope Program (PKH) relates to the conformity of the nominal amount of assistance received by Beneficiary Families (KPM) with the provisions set by the government. The accuracy of the amount of assistance is an important indicator in assessing the effectiveness of the program, because the amount of assistance received will affect the ability of recipient households to meet basic needs, particularly in the education, health, and social welfare sectors. Therefore, an analysis of this aspect was conducted to determine the extent to which the amount of PKH assistance received by KPM in Bandar Lampung City is in accordance with the program provisions and the recipients' perceptions of the adequacy of the assistance. Table 1 shows that 99% of respondents stated that the PKH assistance was in the appropriate amount, while 1% of respondents stated that the amount was not appropriate. Below is a table explaining the distribution of respondents' answers per question item.

Table 3 Distribution of interview results Appropriate Amount PKH assistance

No	Questions	Answer				
		STS	TS	BS	S	SS
1	The amount of assistance that you receive is appropriate	1.0%	3.0%	1.0%	51.0%	44.0%
2	Not cut by irresponsible individuals.	2.0%	0.0%	0.0%	15.0%	83.0%
3	Pregnant women: Rp. 3,000,000 / family / year	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	6.0%	94.0%
4	Early childhood: Rp. 3,000,000,- / family / year	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	7.0%	93.0%
5	Elementary School: Rp. 900,000 / family / year	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	8.0%	92.0%
6	Junior High School: Rp. 1,500,000,- / family / year	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	7.0%	93.0%
7	High School: Rp. 2,000,000,- / family / year	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	6.0%	94.0%
8	Disability: Rp. 2,400,000,-/family/year	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	9.0%	91.0%
9	Seniors: Rp. 2,400,000,-/family/year	1.0%	0.0%	0.0%	7.0%	92.0%

This table presents the responses of Beneficiary Families (KPM) regarding the appropriateness of the amount of PKH assistance received based on their participation components. The results indicate that the majority of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that the amount of assistance received was in accordance with program regulations. Regarding the general appropriateness of the amount of assistance, 95.0% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed, while only a small percentage disagreed.

In the components of assistance for pregnant women, early childhood, and education at the elementary, middle, and high school levels, the majority of respondents also expressed very high levels of agreement. The percentage of respondents who stated they strongly agreed ranged from 91% to 94%, indicating that the amount of assistance in each component was deemed to be in accordance with applicable regulations. A similar trend was observed in the components of assistance for people with disabilities and the elderly, where more than 90% of respondents stated they strongly agreed with the appropriateness of the amount of assistance received.

Based on Table 3, in point 1, which relates to the appropriateness of the amount of PKH assistance received, there were still respondents who stated Strongly Disagree (1.0%), Disagree (3.0%), and Neither Agree (1.0%). This finding indicates that a small

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number of KPM still feel a discrepancy between the assistance received and their needs or the provisions that should be met. In point 2, which discusses the absence of deductions from assistance by irresponsible individuals, there were still respondents who stated Strongly Disagree (2.0%). The presence of respondents who strongly disagree indicates that there are indications of suspected deductions from assistance for a small number of recipients. This indicates the need for stricter oversight and transparency in the distribution of PKH assistance. Furthermore, in point 9, which relates to the elderly assistance component, there were respondents who stated Strongly Disagree (1.0%). This condition indicates that a small number of elderly KPM feel that the amount of assistance received does not fully comply with the provisions or does not reflect their needs. This difference in perception may be caused by a lack of understanding of the PKH assistance scheme or inconsistencies in participant data.

The high level of respondent agreement indicates that the implementation of the Family Hope Program (PKH) in Bandar Lampung City has been effective in terms of the appropriate amount, especially in terms of the conformity of the nominal assistance with program regulations. However, a small number of respondents still expressed disagreement, indicating the need for regular evaluation of the amount of assistance, especially considering the differences in the cost of living in urban areas. This is in line with the statements of PKH facilitators and PKH facilitator coordinators who stated that the amount of assistance received by KPM was appropriate because the aid distribution process was carried out directly through banks or post offices and the withdrawal process must be carried out directly by the recipient.

On time

Timeliness is a key indicator in assessing the effectiveness of the Family Hope Program (PKH) implementation, as the accuracy of the aid distribution schedule significantly impacts the ability of recipient households to plan and meet their basic needs. Social assistance distributed on time is expected to function optimally as a social protection instrument, particularly in maintaining the stability of consumption among poor households. Therefore, an analysis of the timeliness aspect was conducted to determine the extent to which PKH aid distribution in Bandar Lampung City has been in accordance with the disbursement schedule set by the government and the level of recipient satisfaction with this timeliness.

Table 4 Distribution of interview results Appropriate Time PKH assistance

No	Questions	Answer				
		STS	TS	BS	S	SS
1	Receive assistance every three months.	2%	0%	0%	14%	84%
2	Receive assistance in January, April, July, October.	1%	3%	1%	28%	67%
3	I am satisfied with the timely disbursement schedule for PKH assistance.	1%	0%	1%	21%	77%

Table 4 shows the distribution of respondents' responses regarding the timeliness of PKH aid distribution in Bandar Lampung City. Regarding the statement regarding receiving aid distributed every three months, the majority of respondents strongly agreed (84%) and agreed (14%), while the percentage of respondents who disagreed was relatively small. This indicates that the aid distribution schedule generally complies with program regulations.

Furthermore, regarding the timing of aid disbursements in January, April, July, and October, the majority of respondents also gave a positive assessment, with 67% stating they strongly agree and 28% stating they agree. This finding indicates that the PKH aid disbursement schedule is relatively consistent and predictable for Beneficiary Families (KPM). Furthermore, regarding the level of respondent satisfaction with the PKH aid disbursement schedule, the majority of respondents again stated they strongly agree (77%) and agree (21%), indicating a high level of satisfaction with the timeliness of aid distribution.

Based on Table 4, a small proportion of respondents stated Strongly Disagree (STS), Disagree (TS), and Neither Agree (BS) on several questions. In point 1, which relates to receiving assistance regularly every month, there were 2% of respondents who strongly disagreed. The presence of respondents who strongly disagreed indicates that a small proportion of beneficiary families still experience delays or irregularities in receiving monthly assistance. Furthermore, in point 2, there were 1% of respondents who strongly disagreed, 3% who disagreed, and 1% who disagreed. This finding indicates that although the majority of respondents received assistance on schedule, a small proportion of beneficiaries still felt there was an inaccuracy in the disbursement time during certain periods. This could be influenced by differences in disbursement times between regions, banking system constraints, or a less than optimal administrative verification process.

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This situation is caused by technical distribution constraints, administrative issues, or delays in the disbursement process at the local level. In point 3, which concerns respondent satisfaction with the PKH disbursement schedule, 1% of respondents strongly disagreed and 1% disagreed. This indicates that a small proportion of beneficiary families (KPM) are still not fully satisfied. These differences in perception may stem from experiences with delays during certain periods or from a lack of information received by beneficiaries regarding the disbursement schedule.

The predominance of strongly agree responses in the interview results confirms that, overall, beneficiary families assess that PKH distribution in Bandar Lampung City has been carried out on time, in accordance with program regulations. This aligns with statements from PKH facilitators and the statements of the village heads and neighborhood associations (RT) in Bandar Lampung City. Therefore, in terms of timeliness, PKH has been effective in supporting the needs of recipient households.

Right on Target

The appropriateness aspect in the implementation of the Family Hope Program (PKH) relates to the extent to which the assistance received by Beneficiary Families (KPM) is used in accordance with the program's main objectives, namely improving access to and quality of education, health, and the social welfare of poor families. Appropriateness of purpose is an important indicator in assessing the effectiveness of PKH, because the program's success is determined not only by the amount and timeliness of assistance, but also by the suitability of assistance utilization with human resource development targets. Therefore, an analysis of the appropriateness aspect is conducted to determine whether the implementation of PKH in Bandar Lampung City has been running in accordance with the established policy objectives.

Table 5 presents the distribution of respondents' responses regarding the utilization of PKH assistance in accordance with the program's objectives. Regarding the ease of cash transactions through ATMs and BRILink, the majority of respondents strongly agreed (86%) and agreed (13%), indicating that the aid distribution mechanism is considered supportive of appropriate aid utilization. A small number of respondents strongly disagreed (1%). The presence of strongly disagreed respondents indicates that a small number still experience obstacles, such as limited access to banking facilities, distance to ATM/BRILink locations, or a lack of understanding of how to use non-cash transaction services. Therefore, the process of collecting aid funds is assisted by family or PKH facilitators.

Table 5 Distribution of interview results Right on Target PKH assistance

No	Questions	Answer				
		STS	TS	BS	S	SS
1	Transactions at ATMs and Brilink.	1%	0%	0%	13%	86%
2	Buy nutritious food for pregnant women and toddlers, buy school supplies for school children, buy medicines for the elderly and disabled.	2%	0%	0%	11%	87%
3	Implement P2K2 regularly	0%	0%	0%	1%	99%
4	The officer has been to your house	3%	1%	0%	7%	89%

Furthermore, regarding the use of assistance to purchase nutritious food for pregnant women and toddlers, school supplies for children, and medicines for the elderly and people with disabilities, the majority of respondents stated that they strongly agreed (87%) and agreed (11%). There were 2 respondents who strongly disagreed. This finding indicates that although the majority of KPM have utilized assistance according to the program's objectives, there is still a small number of recipients who have not fully utilized PKH assistance for priority needs as stipulated in the program guidelines.

Regarding the regular implementation of Family Capacity Building Meetings (P2K2), almost all respondents expressed a positive assessment, with 99% stating they strongly agreed. This finding indicates that the empowerment and capacity building aspects of recipient families have been running very well. Meanwhile, regarding the visit of companion officers to KPM homes, the majority of respondents also stated they strongly agreed (89%) and agreed (7%), although there were still a small number of respondents who expressed disagreement. There were respondents who stated Strongly Disagree (3%) and Disagree (1%). This condition indicates that although the majority of KPM feel the presence and assistance of PKH officers, there is still a small number of respondents who feel that the companion visits have not been carried out evenly. This could be caused by the limited number of companions, the size of the assistance area, or the intensity of visits that are not optimal. Overall, these results indicate that the implementation of PKH in Bandar Lampung City has been effective in terms of being on target.

PKH Companion stated:

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"It's the right time, even though there are a few things wrong with the use of aid funds"

Figure 5 Interview with Head Field Bandar Lampung City Social Assistance and Security

The primary goal of the Family Hope Program (PKH) social assistance program is to improve the welfare of low-income families. However, in practice, some beneficiaries still use the funds inconsistently with the PKH assistant's instructions. The Head of the Social Assistance and Security Division of Bandar Lampung City stated:

"It's completely correct. Yesterday, we immediately cut off (PKH assistance) for those suspected of online gambling."

Overall, the PKH social assistance program (PKH) is well-targeted, as every response "strongly agree" in the graph reinforces the findings in the previous table, which generally indicates that beneficiaries (KPM) assess the use of PKH assistance as being in line with the program's objectives. However, some beneficiaries (KPM) were still found to be using the funds for online gambling. The findings of beneficiaries engaging in online gambling resulted in their PKH status being immediately terminated, as stated by the Head of the Social Security and Assistance Division of Bandar Lampung City. Therefore, PKH in Bandar Lampung City can be declared effective in terms of its effectiveness.

Proper Administration

The aspect of administrative accuracy is a crucial indicator in assessing the effectiveness of the Family Hope Program (PKH) implementation, as it directly relates to program governance, accountability, and transparency in the distribution of social assistance. Orderly and procedural administration is expected to minimize recording errors, prevent misuse of assistance, and ensure proper reporting and monitoring processes. Therefore, an analysis of the aspect of administrative accuracy was conducted to determine the extent to which Beneficiary Families (KPM) in Bandar Lampung City have understood and implemented the administrative obligations stipulated in the PKH program.

Table 6 presents the distribution of respondents' responses regarding the implementation of administration in the Family Hope Program. Regarding the requirement to submit photocopies of Family Cards (KK), Identity Cards (KTP), and transaction receipts, the majority of respondents strongly agreed (82%) and agreed (15%). There were 1.0% of respondents who strongly disagreed, 1.0% who disagreed, and 1.0% who disagreed. This indicates that the majority of KPM have understood and implemented the administrative obligations stipulated as part of the program's accountability mechanism.

Table 62 Distribution of interview results Amount PKH assistance

No	Questions	Answer				
		STS	TS	BS	S	SS
1	Collect photocopies of your family card, ID card, and transaction receipts.	1.0%	1.0%	1.0%	15.0%	82.0%
2	It is the father's/mother's obligation to report the results of the transaction to the supervisor	0.0%	1.0%	0.0%	15.0%	84.0%

Furthermore, regarding the statement regarding the obligation of beneficiaries to report transaction results to PKH facilitators, the majority of respondents also gave a positive assessment, with 84% stating they strongly agreed and 15% stating they agreed. However, a small number of respondents still expressed disagreement, indicating administrative obstacles for some beneficiaries, such as limited understanding of procedures or technical factors in the reporting process. This requires PKH

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facilitators to further improve the understanding of PKH beneficiaries so that they can fully comply with the applicable administration of the PKH social assistance program.

The predominance of strongly agree responses in the table confirms that, overall, beneficiary families assess the PKH administrative procedures as being well-run and easy to understand. Therefore, from an administrative perspective, PKH in Bandar Lampung City can be considered effective, supported by a high level of administrative compliance from beneficiaries. However, the presence of respondents with a very small negative assessment indicates the need for ongoing mentoring and outreach to continuously improve administrative compliance and maintain consistent program implementation.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on data analysis and field findings, the implementation of the 2022 Family Hope Program (PKH) in Bandar Lampung City was concluded to be effective. This is demonstrated by the alignment between the characteristics of aid recipients and the poverty indicators used in the study, despite an inclusion error of 13 beneficiary families out of 100 respondents.

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